

Research

Solutions to Overcome European Union's Technical Barrier to Vietnamese Textile Export

Nguyen Thi Thanh Thu^{1*}, Xie Zhong¹, Ren Yu Zhe², Pham Thanh Tung³

¹School of Economics, Hefei University of Technology, Hefei, China

²School of civil and transportation engineering, Hohai University, Nanjing, China

³School of Economics, Foreign Trade University, Hanoi, Vietnam

Abstract: Technical barriers are usually used as an effective and legal tool to protect domestic producers, especially in the EU market, more and more sophisticated and complex technical barriers to textile products are being stipulated to hinder the penetration of major exporters, which posed great difficulties for both the government and Vietnamese textile firms, since that textile is Vietnam export pillar and EU is such a potential market yet not fully exploited. Therefore, this paper concentrates on identifying the EU's technical barrier to Vietnamese textile products and analyzes its impact. In addition, it also gives some suggestions to the government and businesses to promote Vietnamese textile export combined with the experience of China. Presently, the drawbacks in the compliance with requirements in EU's TBT mainly concerns environmental and social responsibility standards. Although the Chinese textile industry once was under even more burdensome regulations from the EU than Vietnam, it still managed to overcome these barriers and has become one of the largest textile exporters to the EU due to appropriate governmental supportive policies as well as firms' efforts. Therefore, it is eager that the government and textile businesses cooperate further and more closely in overcoming these technical barriers. From the government's perspective, it is essential to complete their legal framework in harmonization with international standards, closely monitor the TBT application process, provide financial support for technical upgrade and make information about changes in TBT available to give timely warnings and recommendations for businesses. On the other hand, for textile firms' perspective, they must actively develop human resources such as in value-adding activities like designing and marketing as well as implement business strategies for sustainable export by strengthening brand identity and adhering to standards and regulations from importing countries. It is predictable that with the increasing trend of global economic integration and free trade promotion, importing countries will keep up stipulating more types and higher requirements of TBT. Thus, further research on TBT should carefully analyze under the perspective of the government and businesses to see whether there is a missing link in the co-operation of the two participants in overcoming TBT.

Keywords: technical barriers to trade (TBT), European Union (EU), Vietnamese textile, government, business.

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 27 October, 2023; **Published:** 15 November, 2023

How to cite this article: Nguyen Thi Thanh Thu, Xie Zhong, Ren Yu Zhe, Pham Thanh Tung (2023). Solutions to Overcome European Union's Technical Barrier to Vietnamese Textile Export. *North American Academic Research*, 6(10), 69-82. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10138138>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

One of the pillars having the highest export trade volume in Vietnamese economy is the textile industry. In 2021, the export turnover of textile industry reached 40.3 billion USD, which was an increase of 15.2% compared to 2020. According to the Chairman of the Vietnam Textile and Apparel Association (VITAS), Mr. Vu Duc Giang, 2022 is the time when textile enterprises gradually recover from the heavy impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. In the first 8 months of 2022, textile and clothing export turnover was about 31.91 billion USD, up 20.11% over the same period in 2021 and up 21.52% compared to the first 8 months of 2019. This is the highest growth rate over the past 10 years (Web portal of supporting industry of Vietnam 2022). The positive signal of the market and the initial control of the COVID-19 pandemic will help Vietnam's textile and garment industry fulfil its set export target of over 43 billion USD for 2022 (Center for WTO and International Trade). In addition, the rise of many multilateral and bilateral trade agreements such as Free Trade Agreements (FTAs), will open great opportunities for Vietnam to expand market share in favor of tax exemptions to 0% (Trung tâm WTO 2016). Therefore, promoting textile industry in a highly competitive market is one of the main points in Vietnam socio-economic development strategy for the 2021-2025 period. Nevertheless, opportunities always come with challenge. Indeed, in recent years, Vietnamese textile industry has been facing many difficulties, one of which is technical barrier to trade. The major markets for Vietnamese textile products are United States, European Union (EU), Korea and Japan. These are highly potential markets with high demand and a large customer base. However, these markets have strict requirements on consumer safety and environmental protection. Especially, after the strike of economic crisis in 2008, two years of COVID-19 outbreak, political instability in some countries and the surge of multilateral and bilateral trade agreements, many governments have increased the trade protection measures and criteria to protect their domestic producers and revive their economies. As a country engages in international trade and is governed by World Trade Organization (WTO), it is committed to reduce tariffs. Consequently, the government resorts to non-tariff barriers as trade protection measures, in which technical barriers to trade (TBT) becomes the most effective and widely used.

The definition of TBT and its impact were mentioned in research on non-tariff barriers (Coughlin & Wood, 1989; Ho, 2014). Both of them agreed on technical barriers to trade as a form of trade protectionism by giving exporting countries the standard requirements for imported goods. However, Coughlin and Wood also held the view that non-tariff barriers raised price and impeded trade along with an irreversible growing trend of utilizing those barriers (Coughlin & Wood, 1989). Luong concluded that with appropriate measures, there is a chance that countries can take advantage of TBT to compete effectively in international trade (Ho, 2014). There are also many in depth studies on TBT, Marcus witnessed the frustrations of developing countries in conformity with technical regulations, referring it as 'contentious'. Although the notion of technical regulations affects trade patterns, producers' access to new markets and domestic consumers' cost is valid in principle, there is little empirical evidence on do technical regulations actually constrain or promote trade (Maskus, Wilson and Otsuki, 2000). Bao and Qiu used a modified two-stage gravity model with data from TBT notifications of 105 WTO countries during 1995–2008 to support three statements. Firstly, even though a developing country's TBT affects other developing countries' exports, no significant effects are found on the developed countries' exports. Secondly, a developed country's TBT have significant effects on the developing countries exports that of developed countries. Thirdly, exports from developed countries are affected by a developed country's TBT more seriously than that of developing countries (Bao & Qiu 2012).

Moreover, there are various research focusing on TBT imposed on particular countries and measures to overcome such barriers. Ngo analyzed many technical barriers imposed on Vietnamese export, for instance regulations on product quality standards, rules of origins or regulations of packaging and labeling. Some measures are suggested to deal with

these barriers, namely establishing an export strategy, raising businesses' awareness or adopting international standards to enhance product's competitiveness (Ngo, 2018). Additionally, Pham (2014) also gave insight to current situation on Vietnamese textile export and clarifies the rationale and practicality of proposed solutions to overcome the technical barriers set by importing countries such as America, Japan and EU in order to boost Vietnamese textile export (Pham, 2014). Alternatively, Jiang identified types of TBT imposed on Chinese textile from America, EU and Japan, reasons for this imposition and its impact from both positive and negative sides. Finally, the author states some measures for Chinese government as well as enterprises to deal with the current situation (Jiang, 2009). From an Indian perspective, Khorana collected data from questionnaires of sixty companies exporting textile and clothing from India to EU to reveal problems faced by Indian small and medium exporting firms in the presence of trade barriers and some policy implications to tackle those problems (Khorana, Verousis and Perdikis, 2010).

However, the research in depth about the bilateral trade between Vietnam and EU along with the effect of technical barrier to Vietnamese textile products are still lacked. In particular, some research focus on technical barrier to trade on Vietnam exports in general while others concentrate on technical barriers on certain items not textile products. Furthermore, the suggested solutions are also too generalized, governmental oriented and do not keep up with the latest developments of technical barriers to trade. Therefore, the paper aims to identify EU's technical barrier to Vietnamese textile products and analyze its impact. Also, after examining the experience of China, this study gives some suggestions to government and business in order to promote Vietnamese textile export.

Technical barriers

According to The Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT), TBT are defined as 'technical regulations, standards, and conformity assessment procedures', which show no discrimination and do not create any unnecessary distortions to trade. In principle, these measures are necessary and reasonable in order to protect a country's interests of human health or protection of environment. On this ground, it is legitimate for WTO member countries to set up and maintain a system of techniques for their goods and imported goods. However, in practice, TBT can become the potential barrier for international trade by being exploited cunningly, making it difficult for the entry of a foreign goods imported into the country market.

As TBT vary from country to country, it exists various systems of TBT classification as well. Under the perspective of WTO Center and United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), TBT is classified into technical regulations and standards, procedures for conformity assessment, product packaging, eco-labeling, requirements on production methods (PPMs) and consumers requirements, while according to Jiang's research, there are five types of TBT, namely technical standards, technical law and regulations, management regulations of product packing and label, inspection procedures and environmental and ecological standards (Jiang, 2009). However, Pham came up with her own TBT classification, which are summarized as standards and regulations on product quality, standards and regulations on consumer's safety, standards and regulations on environment, standards and regulations on labeling and packaging, standards and regulations on society's responsibility and rules of origin (Pham, 2014). It is worth noting that Pham's TBT classification will be used throughout the analysis of the paper.

Jiang called TBT as a 'double-edged sword', which can have both positive and negative influence on international economy as a whole and countries participating in international trade in particular (Jiang, 2009). In addition, Bao and Qiu also proved that TBT not only affect exporters but also importers, yet these effects depend on 'country's economic development level' (Bao & Qiu, 2010). Therefore, it is essential to analyze influence of TBT from exporter's perspective and importer's perspectives.

From exporter's perspective, on the positive side, firstly, TBT drives technical development to meet the criteria stipulated by importing countries. Secondly, TBT not only protects the producing countries environment but also promotes sustainable development by changing the conception of producers from focusing only on volume manufactured to

concentrating on product’s quality. Thirdly, through complying with labor standards specified in TBT, workers in exporting countries will have better working conditions, improved health and occupational safety, which contributes to the development of modern society. However, on the other hand, the first thing to notice that in accordance with TBT, export cost will increase, profit will decrease, which thus reduces product’s competitiveness of exporting countries.

From importer’s perspective, the first positive influence that TBT creates in importing countries is consumer’s protection, where the provisions in TBT guarantee the quality and safety of goods imported into a market while defected, poor quality goods will be stopped at border and deported back to exporting countries. Secondly, TBT helps protect the importing countries’ environment, in which the product that is not environmentally friendly will not be imported. In addition, these standards contribute to the protection of plants, natural resources while preventing pollution and ecological imbalance. Last but not least, TBT imposes on exporter’s products will increase their cost, price and hence reduce their competitiveness with domestic products. Thus, producers in importing countries are to some extent protected from competition with outsiders for a brief period and have the opportunity to enhance its competitiveness. Meanwhile, protection of domestic producers can have negative side effects. Overly protective producers as a result of TBT will not create enough momentum to compete effectively when the protection ends. Furthermore, since this protection reduces the competitiveness of foreign producers by increasing product’s price, domestic consumer’s choice will be narrow down. Moreover, too strict TBT could lead to retaliation from exporting countries. Since international trade is bilateral or multilateral, seeing the exporting products encounter unreasonable barriers, exporting countries may fight back by create even more high level of barriers. This retaliation will hamper not only countries’ trade relations but also affect international trade negatively.

Current situation of Vietnamese textile industry export to EU

Textile is a vast import and export industry and is directly affected by unpredictable fluctuations in the world. For example, inflation in the US and Europe affects the purchasing power of consumer goods, including textiles, causing orders to tend to decrease. In addition, challenges from large markets such as the US and EU also create pressure for businesses shortly such as the issue of tracing the origin of cotton and Xinjiang cotton products when the ‘Uyghur Forced Labor Prevention Act’ took effect on June 21st, 2022, or the cost of carbon capture, requirements on the content of recycling and reuse for goods imported in the EU market. Facing these difficulties and challenges, in the first seven months of 2022, the EU is still Vietnam’s second largest import market with 2.6 billion USD, up 36.1% over the same period last year. This proves that, in the near future, the EU will still be an important strategic market for Vietnam.

Fig. 1. Vietnamese textile export market share on first 7 months of 2022 (%)

Source: Data from VITAS report July 2022

The EU has 28 countries, with over 500 million people, GDP reached 18.292 billion USD in 2019, accounting for 22% of global GDP (Duc Anh & partner, 2020). In addition, the consumer expenditure on textile products in EU is also high. The EU's share of total world apparel imports increased from 39.75% in 2015 to 43.19% in 2020. According to the European Textile and Apparel Federation (EURATEX), with a household consumption of nearly 500 billion euros, the EU is considered the largest market in terms of volume in the world and has a lot of potential for textile products (Ministry of Industry and Trade, 2020). Currently, China is the largest textile exporter into the EU, followed by Bangladesh, Turkey India, Pakistan, Cambodia and Vietnam. As can be seen in Table 1, other nations, such as Bangladesh, Cambodia, or Pakistan, all enjoy notable benefit in import tax incentives compared to Vietnam when exporting to EU, with the exception of China, which is a 'big boss' in the business. Under the Everything but Arms (EBA) scheme, import taxes are not applicable to Bangladesh, Cambodia, or Pakistan. Pakistan also exempts from import taxes under the GSP+ (Generalised Scheme of Preferences Plus) program. Despite having a GSP preferential tariff scheme as well, Vietnam only has 'Standard GSP' rate, which is 9.6%. The GPS+ and EBA preferential tariff regimes give those suppliers a tremendous competitive advantage in price compared to Vietnam. This also explains why Vietnam's export market share in the EU market remains around 2-3%. Obviously, the competition in the group of developing countries exporting to EU is quite fierce.

Table 1. List of some competitive Asian countries enjoying EU preferential tax programs

Source: The Ministry of Industry and Trade of Vietnam

GPS standard (9.6% import tax)	GPS+(0% import tax) for least developed country	EBA (Tax Free)
Vietnam	Pakistan	Bangladesh
Indonesia	Sri Lanka	Cambodia
India	Philippines	Laos
China		Myanmar

From Fig. 2, it can be clearly seen that more than 70% of textile export is jacket, pants, T-shirt, underwear and shirt. Those products are only suitable for low and middle income market segment. Nevertheless, higher value textile products such as business suit or dress are produced at limited capacity. Moreover, most of the products produced and exported are mainly manufactured from cotton and synthetic fibers.

Fig. 2. Structure of Vietnam’s textile export market in the EU (%)

Source: Calculate data from Vietnam General Department Customs

According to data from Table 2, increasing costs of raw materials, transportation and wages minimum is the main reason that the export price of Vietnam textile products into major markets such as the US, EU, Japan is often 15% to30% higher than the average price compared to other major textile exporting countries such as China, Bangladesh, and India.

Table 2. Vietnamese textile products price exported to major markets compared to some Asian countries in 2013

Source: Data compiled from VITAS annual report and Vietinbank securities report

Country	US – 2013		EU – 2013		Japan – 2013	
	Quantity (bil- lion m ²)	Price (USD/m ²)	Quantity (100 kg)	Price (USD/kg)	Quantity (100 kg)	Price (1000 JPY/kg)
Total	565,257,728	1.85	42,509,495	20.73	18,739,889	1.71
China	271,158,651	1.54	19,263,184	18.26	11,208,793	2.03
Vietnam	36,025,151	2.43	998,344	24.01	1,074,239	2.01
India	37,301,144	1.69	2,083,268	25.95	292,637	1.33
Indonesia	17,262,207	3.03	661,181	23.12	1,277,628	0.86
Bangladesh	19,446,182	2.63	8,154,833	15.21	305,043	1.60

Vietnamese textile export firms typically apply three methods of export. These are Cut-Make-Trim (CMT), Free on Board (FOB) and Original Design Manufacturing (ODM). In 2019, CMT accounted for about 65% of total exports, while more advanced business models such as FOB and ODM accounted only for 35% (Tran 2022). Moreover, Vietnam enterprises exporting by FOB method are mainly FOB level 1 (buying raw materials according to customer’s specifications). Therefore, Vietnamese textile products usually have low value added, which is only approximately 25% of export turnover and has a profit margin of 5-10% (Bui, 2014). There are few firms such as Nha Be, Viet Tien, May 10 or Phong Phu

which can meet the international standards while exporting products under FOB method. Reasons include lack of high-quality human resources, restricted market information, incapability of raising capital or insufficient capital to deal with risk. Thus, in recent years, textile firms in Vietnam have been gradually shifting from ordinary CMT method to processing with FOB and ODM to meet the requirements of the international buyers and generate higher value added.

EU's technical barrier to Vietnamese textile export and its impact

In general, there are several technical barriers that EU applies to textile products from any importer:

Standards and regulations on product quality: The most widely used is ISO 9000 - a set of quality management and quality assurance stipulated by international organizations for standardized use. The standards include the requirements of a quality management system for businesses in general and textile firms in particular. However, ISO 9000 is not required as registration of quality standards is voluntary in most countries. However, under advice from the Information Centre of Business Europe, once the businesses are certified by internationally recognized management standards, their products will enter the market easily. As for the case of EU - a particularly difficult market, ISO 9000 is considered as unwritten mandatory requirement as it can sometimes substitute for certain product quality certification such as 'EN 29002' or 'EN 29003'.

Standards and regulations on consumer's safety: These provisions include regulations on toxic chemicals in textile products which are dangerous to the consumers' health. Toxic chemicals may be carcinogenic aromatic amines (related to azo dyes), the dye spread allergens, heavy metals (cadmium, chromium, lead, mercury, nickel), organic tin compounds (MBT, TBT, TPhT), compounds containing chlorine (organic substances containing chlorine loading as clobenzen, clotoluen), the flame retardants (PBBs, Peta- BDE, octo BDE), formaldehyde, phthalates (DEHP, DINP), total lead content in paint and coated surfaces. The product which is regarded as containing dangerous chemicals will be banned from importing into the foreign markets.

Standards and regulations on environment: Under this regulation, the EU banned the import and sale of textile products containing banned substances. There is a wide range of standards, regulations, rules and laws regarding this issue, such as regulate on the 'registration, evaluation, authorization and restriction of chemicals used' (REACH), ISO 14000 and European Eco - Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS).

Standards and regulations on labeling and packaging: The European Parliament and Council 96/74/EC directive in 1996 specifies in detail how textile products must be labeled in order to enter EU's market, especially in packaging, labeling and size aspects (European Commission, 2006).

Standards and regulations on social responsibilities: The basic content of corporate social responsibility is labor standards which is the standardized set of agreements between multinational companies with worldwide labor unions. Currently, EU uses two international standards SA 8000 and SA 8001, which are stipulated by the International Organization for Social Responsibility. SA 8000 and SA 8001 concern a variety of social responsibility issues such as child labor, workers' health & safety, compensation, discrimination in employment, working hours, trade union freedom.

Rules of origin: EU especially turns its attention to the origin of goods since it concerns whether the goods are entitled to EU's tax. Assessment on the origin of goods is based on raw materials produced in the exporting country.

After European-Vietnam Free Trade Agreement (EVFTA) was approved by the European Parliament on February 12th, 2020, and officially took effect from August 1st, 2020, there were several new features that would affect the textile product exported into EU's market both positively and negatively. On the positive side, firstly, technical barrier creates motivation for firms to invest to improve quality and enhance the competitiveness of their textile products specially to penetrate strictly regulated market such as EU. In fact, Vietnamese textile export to EU market in recent years has increased both in quantity as well as quality in order to strengthen the market share in this potential market, which demonstrates the increasing competitiveness of Vietnamese textile products thanks to the firms' efforts to overcome such rigorous technical barriers. Secondly, technical barrier to textile product also positively impacts the environment.

In order to meet a variety of standards and regulations on environment, firms are forced to turn their attention to environmental protection besides profit as well as come up with effective measures to comply with these standards and regulations. As a matter of fact, many textile firms are putting more effort into protecting the environment such as setting up exhaust treatment system through boiler technology, using rational consumption of materials and fuel, moving the dyeing factories to industrial zones far from city center. Currently, Vietnam has more than ten centers which can test the dyeing substance and more than twenty organizations with capability of checking the authentication level of dye substances. Furthermore, over 200 companies have received Oeko-Tex Standard 100 certificate. Despite its advantages, technical barriers pose some serious challenges to firms when engaging in international trade. The first thing to notice is that technical barriers to textile product increase cost, therefore, reduce the competitiveness of Vietnamese textile product and cause Vietnamese exporters lose their market share. In order to meet the strict standards from EU, textile firms have no other choice but to increase the cost of production by shifting to modern production technology as well as applying advanced management system into production process. However, of more than 6000 textile small and medium sized enterprises in Vietnam, which account for a large proportion, usually retain 2% or 3% of their profit for investment (Bui, 2014). Therefore, a change in technology will result in a financial burden on those companies. If companies do not increase the price of products to cover the increased cost, profit will decline, therefore, the competitiveness of the products on the market decreases. Secondly, technical barrier to textile product indirectly affects lives of workers in this industry. Currently, there are over 2500 workers are employed in the textile industry. Due to the recent economic crisis in Eurozone, besides austerity measures enacted, EU also raises the standards of technical barriers such as increasing in criteria of safety quality control system or tighten the control of chemicals and substances used in imported textile products. To meet these increasing quality requirements, businesses who want to lower the cost of products in order to increase competition in the EU may resort to a cut in workforce. In the long run, this cut will cause employees who are not assured of their job will switch to other occupations, which will destabilize the supply of raw materials and labor resources for textile industry.

The experience of China

In 1995, the EU became China's third largest trade partner in textile and clothing following Japan and USA (Policy Research Center for Environment and Economy 1999). The surge of Chinese textile and clothing export to EU did not stop. On October 13th, 2004, it was not until October 2007 that EU finally seized to limit the textile exportation from China. Since then, China has become one of the largest exporters of textile and clothing products to the EU, ahead of the top three Mediterranean exporters to the EU, namely Turkey, Tunisia, and Morocco, in spite of their duty- and quota-free benefits. According to China Textile Federation, in 2020, the textile industry strongly overcame the significant impact of the new crown epidemic. In 2020, China was the top ranked global textile and clothing exporter, more than 280.5 billion USD, in which 71.7 billion USD is from EU market. The main textile products exported to EU are textile and clothing through Original Equipment Manufacturing (OEM) method. However, in 2021, China's textile export to EU dropped by 13.5%, mainly dragged down by the decrease in the amount of textile exports due to the depreciation of Euro, the continuing slow growth of consumer demand and excess production capacity. More statistics about China textile and clothing trade with EU from 2017 to 2021 can be found in the Table 3.

Table 3. China textile and clothing trade with EU from 2017 to 2021*Source: Collect data from Trademap*

		2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
World	Export (billion USD)	257.8	266.4	260.2	280.5	304.7
	Change (%)	-	3.3	-2.3	7.8	8.6
	Share (%)	100	100	100	100	100
EU (28 countries)	Export (billion USD)	54.8	55.7	52.7	71.1	61.5
	Change (%)	-	1.6	-5.4	34.9	-13.5
	Share (%)	21.3	20.9	20.3	25.3	20.2

Currently, China is facing several technical barriers to textile products which mainly involves health and safety regulations, Eco labeling and policies for chemical products. Since 1994, due to 'Second Amendments to the Consumer Protection Act' issued by the German government, the use of azo dyes in textile products has been prohibited (European Commission 1994). Since April 1997, the 5th Amendments to the German Consumer Protection Act contain more specific provisions, which includes a list of products affected by the azo ban, namely clothing, bedding materials, towels, masks, diapers (The Ecological and Toxicological Association of Dyes and Organic Pigment Manufactures 1998). Moreover, in April 1996, the Commission of the European Communities established its ecological criteria for Eco-label of T-shirts and bed-linen, which is still applied until now (European Commission 1996). Other eco-labeling programs are either national such as the 'Sweden Good Environmental Choice', or privately certified by some international institution, for instance 'Oeko-Tex Standard 100' and 'Tex-proof' in Germany. Regarding other substance such as Formaldehyde or PCB, PCT, 'The Dangerous Substance Act' in 1994 also clearly stated textiles contain formaldehyde of more than 1500 ppm must bear labels stating, 'This product contains formaldehyde, and users are advised to wash the product before wearing so that skin can adjust to it.'

China has always been one of the most active countries to take advantage of multilateral and bilateral agreements. Through actively participating in negotiations, Chinese governments not only settled disputes effectively and legally but also eliminated doubt and created trust in the international community about the quality and safety of its textile products. For example, as a result of the termination of The Agreement on Textile and Clothing (ATC) in 2005, Chinese textile export increased dramatically causing EU to impose more barriers. After 10 hours of negotiation, EU and China came to terms with a win-win situation on June 10 (European Commission 2005). In particular, China got a favorable textile export growth rate as well as a package of arrangements at a low cost. In addition, the agreement to use 'Paragraph 242' paved up the path for a stable penetration into EU market of Chinese textile products. Additionally, Chinese government has put much effort into promoting the application of international standards along with passing laws and regulations accordingly. In 2010, 70-80% of Chinese product's standard is lower than international standards and machinery are behind those of developed countries by 10 to 20 years (Pham, 2014). Therefore, during the past few years, the government through propaganda and regulations has encouraged business to adopt international standards such as ISO 9000 standard for quality assurance and quality management, ISO 14000 for environmental management standards despite having these standards is not mandatory. As a result, on December 12th, 2012, ISO published survey results of certified management system standard worldwide by the end of 2011 in which three countries with the most granted

ISO 9001:2008 and ISO 14001:2004 certificates are China, Italy and Japan (The International Organization for Standardization Survey, 2012). Last but not least, in order to increase the competitiveness of Chinese textile product, the government always takes textile industry into consideration when establishing development goals. In April 2006, the State Development and Reform Commission released the 'Notice on Several Opinions on Accelerating Restructuring to Facilitate the Upgrading of the Textile Industry', which concerns the restructure and technological application in manufacturing process. The building of brand names is another priority in these plans. A campaign named 'Ten Thousand Miles March for Brand Building' was enacted in which companies whose brand names are certified as 'famous' will be awarded with free media coverage and money. It is reported that Ningbo City provided awards to companies that export textiles and apparel products under their own foreign-registered brand names.

For the business perspective, one significant change that Chinese textile firms have made while overcoming EU's TBT is the gradual shift in the value adding activities. In the past, Chinese textile firms mainly involved in production and processing, which does not generate much added value. However, in recent years, with the support of Chinese government, many major textile exporting firms such as Youngor Group or Ningbo Shanshan Company have switched from original CMT to OEM method, which has led to higher revenue gain as well as an increase in textile export (Stewart 2007). Secondly, as social responsibility and environmental standards have always been the most challenging technical barriers to Chinese textile products, Chinese textile firms have begun to implement strict labor regulations, clinging to the notion of human-oriented and maintaining the rights of workers. Moreover, Chinese enterprises also established a mechanism of stringent quality supervision to adapt to the 'green barrier' requirements. Chinese major textile firms in recent years have strictly complied with environmental regulations in the entire manufacturing process from collecting raw materials, production, design, packaging and disposal after use of garments in order to promote environmental protection according to international standards.

Suggestions to overcome EU's technical barrier to Vietnamese textile export

SWOT analysis

Strength: Cheap cost of labor is one of the most important advantages that developing countries especially Vietnam currently holds. Due to this factor, Vietnamese textile products have increased rapidly in recent years. As a result, Vietnamese worker wage in the textile industry is one of the lowest rates in the world, which is 151 USD/month (Davis & Lu, 2020) approximately 1.5 times lower than that of a Chinese worker. Despite the wage paid is low, Vietnamese worker is considered to be skilled and able to learn new skills quickly. On the one hand, this factor allows manufacturers of Vietnam to recruit and train workers quickly with low training costs. On the other hand, skilled workers create a high-quality but inexpensive human resource for every textile company desire. In addition, since the textile industry has always been considered Vietnamese export pillar and received long-term support from the government. Prior to the pandemic, by building more textile-specific industrial parks and boosting domestic supporting industries, the government had already prioritized assisting the textile sector. Besides providing funds, tax incentives, financial assistance and creating favorable conditions for market access have been actively provided by the government. Also, Economic and political stability is essential. Typically known as the peaceful country, Vietnam has showed the world the image of a stable economy without much political unrests. This factor is essential for foreign investors to consider when pouring money into a project overseas. According to the UNCTAD, in the first 11 months of 2019, Vietnam attracted Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) capital to the garment and textile industry with a value up to 1.55 billion USD for 184 projects. Investments were led by Hong Kong (447 million USD), Singapore (370 million USD), China (270 million USD), and South Korea (165 million USD) (Nguyen, 2020).

Weakness: Despite low cost of labor, production costs for textile products are relatively high comparing to China, India and Pakistan due to low labor productivity, high production cost such as electricity, internet, telephone and especially transportation due to geographical distance and further customs procedures for imported raw material. These raw ma-

materials used in production are mainly imported from China, which increases product's price and hence reduce the product's competitiveness in foreign market. Additionally, the huge geographical distance between Vietnam and EU and custom procedures for imported raw material do not only increase product cost but also prolong the production time. On the other hand, since the removal of quotas on May 1st, 2005, in ATC, international customers have increasingly sought textile manufacturers rather than through domestic agency. However, there are few Vietnamese textile manufacturers capable of providing full service due to insufficient capacity in the design, sourcing of materials and implementation of logistics operations. Furthermore, the textile industry lacks highly skilled workers such as technicians, marketing personnel, managers, and mid-level designers. In the past, most of the Vietnamese textile manufacturers only focused on CMT and passively sought customers. However, the shift from labor-intensive CMT and FOB to higher value generating method such as OEM and ODM among large textile firms in the world requires compatible human resources.

Opportunities: As analyzed above, the removal of quotas on textiles and clothing to the EU market for Vietnam on May 1st, 2005, could still been a wonderful opportunity for Vietnam's textile industry to increase its export. In addition, due to the EVFTA agreements, EU agreed to reduce its tariff rate for Vietnamese textile product to 0 in 7 years, which is a good chance for Vietnamese textile firms to increase its export and increase their products' effectiveness. With the deeper integration of Vietnam into the international market over the past few years such as ascension to WTO and EVFTA agreement, it facilitated better market access for textiles and attracted higher FDI as well as access to technological advances from developed countries. It is noting that one of the most significant changes in EVFTA agreements is that fabrics need to be manufactured in Vietnam with only the exception of Korea. This provision will be a motive for Vietnam to gain autonomy in the supply of raw material, which will reduce production costs and shorten the time of the production process. Furthermore, initiatives in customs procedures such as electronic customs procedures and priority booking on customs procedures have been deployed. The selective customs inspection is being implemented based on new customs legislation adopted in 2006 can also shorten production time for textile export.

Threats: Increasing level of non-tariff barriers: In the context of reducing tariff to promote trade liberalization, many countries especially seek technical barriers concerning social responsibility and environmental standards, anti-subsidy, or anti-dumping measures to protect domestic producers. However, the majority of Vietnam textile industry is small and medium sized enterprises, which do not have enough resources to pursue lawsuit when trade disputes occur. Meanwhile, trade barriers have become increasingly sophisticated and more flexible especially during financial crisis and recession. Besides, the legal documents are still in the process to be in harmonization with international standards, while the capability of officials who involve in policy planning is limited. Additionally, despite the Government's policy to encourage investment in the auxiliary industry but the local authorities tend not to attract much investment in the dyeing industry due to environmental issues.

Suggestions

For government's perspective, firstly, as mentioned above, the harmonization rate of national standards with international standards is still low, therefore, it is urgent that the government improve their legal framework to meet the international recognized standards such as quality standards, environmental standards, social responsibility standards, consumer's safety standards or intellectual property issues. In addition, the government must strictly control the product quality from the beginning of the manufacturing process. Secondly, due to the constantly changing in TBT, government should put more consideration into overcoming these TBT to boost export by stipulating stricter legal frameworks to enforce firm into complying with these barriers. In addition, the overcoming TBT issue must be included in the socio-economic development plans and governmental orientations and guidance must be clear, concise, and not contradictory so that firms can follow accordingly. Thirdly, one of the challenges for textile firms to overcome technical barriers is that these barriers are subject to continuous change. Meanwhile, textile firms in the developing and LDCs often have difficulty in understanding and gathering information related to these barriers because of unavailable resources and

weak information systems. Therefore, specialized agencies such as Vietnam Chamber of Commerce and Industry or Vietnam TBT Office must constantly monitor and update information about technical barriers and make the information available and businesses. Furthermore, these specialized agencies should organize workshops, meetings about new changes so that firms can adjust timely and accordingly. Fourthly, these policies can be in form creating favorable legal framework for investment in technical upgrade, cleaner manufacturing process, advanced quality management system, application of environmental standards and social responsibility in accordance with international standards, researches on value adding activities such as designing, marketing or credit policy such as long-term loan with low interest using ODA funds, deferred payment of foreign suppliers or favorable conditions for private firms to access to capital. Also researches, surveys to discover if there are any difficulties and challenges in the process in order to adjust policies accordingly need to be done regularly. Last but not least, the government should support domestic exporters in trade disputes by negotiations with foreign party in terms of legal counseling or financial aid to pursue lawsuits if necessary to keep the reputation of the company as well as the prestige of Vietnamese textile products in the international market. Fifthly, the government should organize exhibitions, workshops and propaganda to promote and raise awareness of textile firms about consumer's health safety. Moreover, the government should also establish independent rating agencies, ecological laboratories, which have the capability of testing and granting safety standard certification as well as guiding textile firms to comply with regulations concerning safety standards from importing countries.

For business's perspective, firstly, textile firms should actively invest in advanced quality management systems, modern technology and improve transparency of the raw materials' origin to ensure it meets the standards of the importing countries. Secondly, the link among businesses can help develop product diversification and take advantage of division of labor. In addition, this link can ensure sustainable growth and reduce manufacturing costs through economies of scale and of scope. Besides, for orders of large volume, joint ventures among domestic firms as well as foreign agents are required. Thirdly, in the context of increasing trade liberalization and deeper integration into the world's economy, technical barrier to textile products is inevitable. Therefore, textile firms need to develop a sustainable business strategy from the raw materials' acquisition to finished product. The business strategy must aim at improving the quality of products based on advanced equipment and modern techniques, application of advanced quality management and compliance with environmental standards or social responsibility standards. Fourthly, instead of waiting to be forced and closely monitor to adapt to new regulations, textile firms must actively learn, innovate to catch up with these regulations. In order to do that, textile firms must carefully study the rules especially after EVFTA to ensure they meet the standards before exporting. In addition, they should determine its own business strategy depending on specific conditions, either to take advantage of the available raw material resources to dominate the domestic market and then promote export or to build their own supply chain within the foreign country.

Conclusion

In the context of promoting trade liberalization, even though countries are set out to gradually eliminate barriers to trade, technical barriers are used more frequently as an effective and legal tool to protect domestic producers. In strict market as EU, more and more sophisticated and complex technical barriers textile products are being stipulated to hinder the penetration of from major exporters. Those barriers pose great difficulties for both the government and Vietnamese textile firms, especially when textile is Vietnam export pillar and EU is such a potential market yet not fully exploited. Therefore, this study focuses on identifying EU's technical barrier to Vietnamese textile products and analyzes its impact. Combined with the experience of China, this study gives some suggestions to government and business in order to promote Vietnamese textile export. Recently, there are still some drawbacks in the compliance with requirements in EU's TBT, mainly concerns with environmental and social responsibility standards. Chinese textile industry once was in even harder regulations from EU than Vietnam. Nevertheless, it still managed to overcome these barriers and has become one of the largest textile exporters to EU due to appropriate governmental supportive policies as well

as firms' efforts. Therefore, it is urgent that the government and textile businesses co-operate further and more closely in overcoming these technical barriers. As for the government, they need to complete their legal framework in harmonization with international standards, closely monitor the TBT application process, provide financial support for technical upgrade and make information about changes in TBT available to give timely warnings and recommendations for businesses. As for textile firms' responsibilities, they must actively develop human resources such as in value-adding activities such as designing and marketing as well as implement business strategies for sustainable export by strengthening brand identity and adhering to standards and regulations from importing countries. It is foreseeable that as the trend of global economic integration and free trade promotion will continue in the future, importing countries will continue to stipulate more types and higher requirements of TBT. Therefore, further research on TBT should carefully analyze under the perspective of the government and businesses to see whether there is a missing link in the co-operation of the two participants in overcoming TBT.

References

- [1] Bao Xiaohua and Qiu Larry D. Do Technical Barriers to Trade Promote or Restrict Trade? Evidence from China. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Accounting & Economics*, 2010; 17.3, 253-278.
- [1] Bao Xiaohua and Qiu Larry D. How Do Technical Barriers to Trade Influence Trade. *Review of International Economics*, 2012; 20.4, 691-706.
- [2] Coughlin Cletus C. and Wood Geoffrey E. *An Introduction to Non-Tariff Barriers to Trade*. St. Louis: Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, 1989.
- [3] European Commission. Directive 94/10/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council Of 23 March 1994. European Commission, 1994.
- [4] European Commission. Commission Decision of 22 April 1996 establishing the ecological criteria for the award of the Community eco-label to bed linen and T-shirt. European Commission, 1996.
- [5] European Commission. Directive 96/74/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council Of 16 December 1996 on Textile Names. European Commission, 2006.
- [6] European Commission. Study On China's Textiles & Clothing Industry and Its Market Expansion Strategy. European Commission, 2005.
- [7] The International Organization for Standardization Survey. *The ISO Report of Management System Standard Certification – 2012*, 2012.
- [8] The Ecological and Toxicological Association of Dyes and Organic Pigment Manufactures. German Ban of use of certain azo compounds in some consumer goods. ETAD Information Notice No 6, 1998.
- [9] Jiang Ningchuan. Effect Of Technical Barriers to Trade on Chinese Textile Product Trade. *IBR* 1.3 1-7, 2009.
- [10] Khorana Sangeeta, Verousis Thanos, and Perdakis Nicholas. *Perceptions of Export Problems in EU - India Trade: Evidence from Small and Medium Firms*. United Kindom: Aberystwyth University, 2010.
- [11] Maskus Keith E., Wilson John S., and Otsuki Tsunehiro. *Quantifying The Impact of Technical Barriers to Trade: A Framework for Analysis*. World Bank Development Group, 2000.
- [12] Stewart Terence P. *China's Support Programs for Selected Industries: Textiles and Apparels*. USA: Trade Lawyers Advisory Group, 2007.
- [13] Policy Research Center for Environment and Economy. *Impacts Of Environmental Standards and Requirements in EU Countries on China's Textile Industry*. China: Policy Research Center for Environment and Economy, 1999.
- [14] Davis Emma and Lu Sheng. *Minimum Wage Level for Garment Workers in the World*, 2020.
- [15] Bui Van Tot. *Textile And Apparel Industry Report*. Hanoi: FPT securities, 2014.
- [16] Phạm Thị Lụa. *Rào cản kỹ thuật đối với hàng dệt may xuất khẩu và giải pháp của Việt Nam (Pham Thi Lua, Technical Barriers for Textile and Garment Exports and Solutions from Vietnam)*, 2014.

- [17] Hồ Thị Hoàng Lương. Ảnh Hưởng Của Hàng Rào Kỹ Thuật Tới Hoạt Động Ngoại Thương Của Việt Nam (Ho Thi Hoang Luong, The Impact of Technical Barriers on Vietnam's Foreign Trade). Nghệ An: Đại học Kinh tế Nghệ An (Nghe An: Nghe An University of Economics), 2014.
- [18] Trung tâm WTO. Dệt May Việt Nam Đón Cơ Hội Từ Những FTA Thế Hệ Mới. Liên đoàn thương mại và công nghiệp Việt Nam. (Center for WTO and International Trade, Vietnam Chamber of Commerce and Industry, Vietnam Textile and Garment Takes Opportunity from New Generation FTAs), 2016.
- [19] Center for WTO and International Trade. Garment and textile Industry see export prospects in 2022. Vietnam Chamber of Commerce and Industry, 2022.
- [20] Ngô Dương Minh. Những rào cản đối với các doanh nghiệp Việt Nam khi tham gia vào chuỗi giá trị dệt may toàn cầu. (Ngo Duong Minh, Barriers for Vietnamese Businesses to Participate in the Global Textile Value Chain). Journal of Economic & Banking Studies (JEBS), 2018.
- [21] Đức Anh và cộng sự. Tác động của Hiệp định EVFTA đối với ngành dệt may Việt Nam (Duc Anh and partners, Impact of the EVFTA Agreement on Vietnam's Textile and Garment Industry). Vietnam National Textile and Garment Group, 2020.
- [22] Ministry of Industry and Trade of Vietnam. Thông tin xuất khẩu vào thị trường EU: Mặt hàng dệt may (Information about Exporting to the EU Market: Textile and Garment Products). Center for WTO and International Trade, Vietnam Chamber of Commerce and Industry, 2020.
- [23] Nguyen Trinh. Seizing Investment Opportunities in Vietnam's Garment and Textile Industry. Vietnam Briefing, 2020.
- [24] Tran Hoang Phu Xuan. The Journey to Sustainability in Fashion. Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation, 2022/CTI/SYM1/014, 2022.
- [25] In August 2022, Vietnam's Textile and Garment Exports Reached Their Highest Level. Web portal of supporting industry of Vietnam. 2022.

